

Grand Unified Theory Of Everything: Local hidden variables, ether gravity Relativity; No Bell theorem, superposition of states, entanglement, quantum computers, QED, or strings

Abstract

This article describes a local-realistic hidden-variables model of the internal structure of elementary particles, compatible, in principle, with all experimental results presently available, including Bell's inequality tests. According to this model, there exists an absolute space, ether or vacuum. Electromagnetic radiation consists of ether waves interacting linearly. Matter is formed by packets of ether waves trapped by non-linear interaction mechanisms. Elementary particles are packets of this type forming regularly spaced lattices. Lorentz transformation reflects the effect of Pythagoras' theorem on the interaction lines holding together material objects moving relative to ether. The contraction of these objects makes the Michelson-Morley experiment compatible with the existence of ether. The time shifts generated by this motion along its direction in regularly spaced structures produce a wave identifiable with de Broglie's phase wave. The resulting variant of the Bohr-Sommerfeld model, in which electrons occupy their entire orbits, can reproduce the experimental results of the whole Quantum physics and chemistry. The model can also reproduce Newtonian gravity and General Relativity in terms of ether density acting as refraction index on the deflection of ether waves of both matter and radiation, replacing the concepts of space-time and its curvature.

The model is entirely based on real numbers and is incompatible with Schrödinger's equation and its associated complex wave function and operators in their current formulation, and also with the concepts of quantum superposition of states and entanglement, and therefore with quantum computers as currently planned, with exponential performance. It also predicts a limit for a safe motion of macroscopic objects at around $c/1000$. In the practical aspect, the model can be tested against some predictions of today's Relativity and Quantum theories with technologies that are already available at reasonable costs, or will probably be developed or perfected in the near future.

Keywords: Special Relativity, General Relativity, Newtonian gravitation or gravity, Hidden-variables model, Bohr-Sommerfeld model, Wave-particle duality, Bell's inequality test, Ether or Aether, Grand Unified Theory, Grand Unification Theory, Theory Of Everything, Absolute time, Quantum physics, Fine structure constant inverse integer, Quantum Field Theory, Quantum computers, Quantum gravity, Electrostatic force, Electrodynamics, Quark confinement, Strong interaction range.

Foreword

Treat others as you would want to be treated

(The Golden Rule, proclaimed in a plethora of major texts dealing with ethics and wisdom)

Unfortunately, a theoretical ‘scientific’ proof of this precept is probably impossible, according to the most usual meanings given today to the word ‘science’. The Golden Rule, like practically any other possible statement about collective or individual human behaviour, is probably an undecidable statement in terms of Gödel’s theorems (consider a hypothetical theory of all human minds). Anyway, the fact is that today’s **‘science’ has apparently been unable to prove the most important principle of civilization... and therefore of science itself**. By contrast, a practical proof of the Golden Rule is given by the fact that, in the long term, only civilizations based on this principle, at least nominally, have survived.

The Golden Rule is cited here because the lack of compliance with this principle can make science and technology useless, if not plainly harmful.

“Science sans conscience n’est que ruine de l’âme” (*Rabelais*)

Preliminary note

In order to minimize the probability of errors, and also to make the article understandable for as many readers as possible, the author has avoided or simplified the treatment of all the subjects that seemed too complicated to allow an analysis with a degree of reliability as close to certainty as readers deserve. A more exhaustive procedure would have been of limited interest, because the fact that a theory agrees with all known experiments, however strictly, does not prove that it is correct, since it might be invalidated in the future by more advanced tests. Nevertheless, it is possible to test the theory presented here in comparison with the predictions of today’s Relativity and Quantum theories. Several experiments suitable for this purpose are discussed at the end of this article.

“Keep It Simple and Straightforward” (*A well-known principle of technical design*)

1. Background

It is well known that Relativity and Quantum theories contain a variety of controversial aspects [1,2,3], in addition to being incompatible with each other, at least in their current standard forms [4,5]. This article proposes a new model of matter and radiation that unifies all branches of theoretical physics, without these controversial aspects, by keeping and developing the parts of these branches that remain compatible with one another. It will be shown point by point that this model complies with present experimental evidence, although some of its predictions diverge from those of today’s theories, which it will be possible to verify as technology advances.

2. Description

The basis of the model is a physical medium filling the entire space, which we will call *vacuum* or *ether* [6], endowed at each point with at least one scalar physical magnitude, the *density*, which in a first approximation could be identified with the electric potential. Up to a certain level, local differences of density can propagate through vacuum as waves,

as in classical Maxwell's theory. However, above (perhaps also below) some threshold level, the behaviour of vacuum becomes a sort of condensation or explosion resulting in a more isotropic redistribution of the directions of the incoming waves, including a partial reflection. This non-linear behaviour differentiates matter from pure radiation, and this reflection is what allows matter to remain immobile in vacuum or travel at velocities far lower than light. These non-linear events will be called here *material events*, and they occur at *material points*, which are represented in the figures by small black-filled circles. All possible density changes travel through vacuum at the speed of light. Matter structures consist of a set of waves that are stationary when matter is immobile relative to ether, and converge periodically at matter points.

The model leaves open the precise detail of the laws determining the local properties of ether. This gives to the model the potential to explain practically any physical phenomenon at the highest precision level achieved so far by experiments, although some of these calculations might be complicated.

3. Special Relativity

With the sole assumption that matter is formed by periodic interactions travelling at the speed of light, the model accounts for all the experimental results supporting Special Relativity (SR). We can deduce the formulas of Lorentz-Fitzgerald length contraction and Lorentz-Larmor time dilation from elementary geometry and classical kinematics, as represented in Figure 1.

The application of Pythagoras' theorem to the triangle $A_0B_1B_1'$ gives:

$$c^2 t'^2 = c^2 t^2 + v^2 t^2,$$

hence the Lorentz-Larmor time dilation:

$$t' = \frac{t}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}}$$

For the longitudinal interactions, we have:

$$c(t' + t_d) = v t_d + l' + vt'$$

$$c(t' - t_d) = v t_d + l' - vt'$$

and, by applying the above value for t' and noting that $l = ct$, we obtain the Lorentz-Fitzgerald length contraction formula:

$$l' = l \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}$$

Figure 1- Special Relativity

The first drawing represents a part of a material structure at rest relative to the observer, who is in turn at rest relative to ether. The structure contains four material points A, B, C and D, where three different lines of interaction starting at the same instant 0 from A, C and D converge on B at a later instant t. We suppose $AB = CB = DB = l = ct$.

In the second drawing, the material structure moves towards the right with speed v relative to ether. Because of the movement, the interactions will have to converge at point B_1' because the point B, by then, will have moved to B_1 from the (possibly virtual) position B_1 it occupied when the interaction was initiated at A. Similarly, the interactions generated at C and D, starting respectively at points C_0 and D_0 , will also converge at B_1' at the same time as $A_0 \rightarrow B_1'$. However, since $C_0B_1' > D_0B_1'$, the interaction CB must start at C_0 a certain time t_d before that of A_0 , and DB must start the same time t_d after that of A_0 (because of symmetry). We will call l' the new characteristic length of the structure along the direction of the movement, and t' the new characteristic time determined by the propagation of the transversal interaction $A_0 \rightarrow B_1'$.

4. Quantum phenomena

If, at rest, the interactions of the preceding discussion are part of a stationary oscillation of wavelength equal to the Compton wavelength $\lambda_c = h / mc$ of the particle, when this particle moves with speed v the successive time shifts t_d occurring over each distance λ_c will generate a phase wave in the direction of the movement, with wavelength

$$\lambda_b = \lambda_c \cdot \frac{t'}{t_d} = \lambda_c \cdot \frac{c}{v} = \frac{h}{mv}$$

that is, De Broglie's wavelength.

Furthermore, over a closed trajectory or 'chain' of interactions, the total phase shift must equal a whole number of cycles. Therefore we must have, ds being the line element of the orbit:

$$\oint \frac{t_d}{t'} \cdot \frac{ds}{\lambda_c} = \oint \frac{v}{c} \cdot \frac{mc}{h} \cdot ds = \oint \frac{mv}{h} \cdot ds = n ,$$

so

$$\oint p \cdot ds = nh$$

which is the Bohr-Sommerfeld quantization rule. We can note that this condition remains valid if v or λ_c vary along the trajectory.

The drawings at the left of the figure represent the whole hydrogen atom in its ground state, viewed from two different directions. The material part of the electron, roughly toroidal and occupying its entire orbit, is represented in grey. The surrounding electric field, without matter, but inseparable from the material part, is represented in white. The nucleus, a proton or deuteron, is the small black point at the centre. At the right side of the figure, the material points of the electron and their interaction lines, which become field lines outside the material part, are represented in detailed section views. The circumference of the orbit contains 137 times the spacing of the material point network along this circumference. The succession of consecutive material events along the orbit forms De Broglie's phase wave, which travels along the material points at 137 times the speed of light. This is possible because the progression of the wave does not result from direct interactions, but from a previously established global synchronism. The interactions between the points travel at speed c , and the electron structure itself rotates at effective speed $c/137$. In other words, one interaction step between contiguous material points corresponds to one full rotation of De Broglie's wave along the orbit, and to $1/137^2$ rotation of the electronic structure. For clarity, 5 points have been represented in each transversal dimension; this number is not a consequence of the basic theory, but it will be justified in section 9.3. No effort has been made to respect the real proportions of the represented objects, which, anyway, cannot be measured and cannot be calculated with precision in the context of the model presented here, at least as long as a precise propagation equation or law has not been defined. Further details about these points will be given in the section about QED.

5. General Relativity

The experimental results presently accounted for by General Relativity (GR) can be deduced from the assumptions made for SR plus the postulate that as one approaches a big mass the speed of light in vacuo decreases in the amounts calculated below. The deduction from this gradient of c of the features of GR is explained below with the aid of Figure 3.

5.1 Newtonian gravitation

We consider a big quasi-spherical mass M and work with radial coordinates r , φ , centred on this mass. G is the universal gravitation constant.

We can calculate the gradient of speed of light on the basis of the mechanism illustrated in Fig.2, by deducing the gradient of c from the relation between the downwards speed of Fig.2 and the time shift t_d explained in Fig. 1, which is a consequence of the gradient of c . One finds that, to explain quantitatively Newtonian gravity, we must have, at least for $r \gg r_s$, where r_s is the Schwarzschild radius $2GM/c^2$:

$$\frac{dc}{dr} = \frac{2GM}{cr^2}$$

and therefore the speed of light at radial coordinate r must be

$$c(r) = c_\infty \cdot \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2 r}\right) = c_\infty \cdot \left(1 - \frac{r_s}{r}\right)$$

Figure 3- Effect of gravity on matter

The first drawing represents five material points of a material structure at rest without gravity, with arrows representing interactions. The second drawing represents the same structure inside a vertical gravitational field g . For clarity, we suppose that initially the vertical speed is 0; otherwise, the representation would be more difficult, because the material events at A, (C, D) and E would not be simultaneous. The interactions now converge at B', because light is faster in the upper part of the figure. Therefore, the structure has moved downwards, so it has been accelerated. If the structure also moves towards the right with speed v , then B' becomes B'', which implies an additional downwards movement causing the precession of elliptical orbits. The proportions have been adapted for reasons of visibility.

5.2 Light deflection

It is now possible to predict the deflection of light rays by massive objects by calculating the curvature radius resulting from the difference of advance of the wavefront at radii r and $r+dr$, on the basis of the difference of c at these radii deduced from the above result for $c(r)$. We find that if the distance of maximum approach of the ray to the centre of the mass is D , the total deflection of this ray is

$$\Delta\alpha = \frac{4GM}{Dc^2}$$

which is the GR result.

5.3 Orbital precession

We note that the usual GR calculation of this effect is based on the intermediate result

$$\frac{d^2u}{d\varphi^2} + u = \frac{GM}{K^2} + \frac{3GMu^2}{c^2}$$

followed only by classical calculations, where $u = 1/r$ and K is a constant [7]. The first term of the second member corresponds to Newtonian gravitation, and the second term to the deflection of light rays. Therefore, since our model predicts the same values as GR for both these magnitudes, it should also provide the same value as GR for the precession of elliptical orbits.

5.4 Gravitational time dilation and redshift

For time dilation, the comparison of their respective formulas suggests that the reproduction of GR or reality by our model cannot be based only on the decrease of light speed inside the gravitational field. We would have to admit an additional contribution in the form of a reduction of the Compton wavelength, which cannot be deduced from Fig.2, but seems realistic: we could assume that, as it descends the gravitational field, the material structure slightly shrinks in order to compensate in part the reduction of light speed. As for redshift, both our model and GR predict a wavelength proportional to the inverse radius, resulting, in the case of our model, from the variations of c along the field.

5.5 Delay of radar signals

The precise comparison of the predictions of our model with currently available experimental data is excluded here for reasons of volume and complexity. However, for illustrative purposes, we provide a simplified calculation for a light ray or radar signal traveling along a rectilinear trajectory $E-H-P$ and back, near a big mass M centred at O so that OH is perpendicular to EHP and distance $OH = D$. We calculate the delay of a radar signal over the trajectory $EHPHE$. We simplify by dividing the calculation of each side of H into two parts, in each of which, X being a point inside EHP , we make the approximations ($r = OX$):

$$r \approx D \text{ for } HX < D$$

$$r \approx HX \text{ for } HX > D$$

In this way, the model gives, for the round trip, a delay Δt for the radar signal with respect to its travel time on the same distances far from big masses:

$$\Delta t \approx \frac{4GM}{c^3} \cdot \left[\ln \left(\frac{4r_E r_P}{D^2} \right) + 1.3 \right]$$

where $r_E = OE$ and $r_P = OP$.

The result of GR is [8]:

$$\Delta t \approx \frac{4GM}{c^3} \cdot \left[\ln \left(\frac{4r_E r_P}{D^2} \right) + 1 \right]$$

5.6 GR Summary

The model implies that the effect of gravity on matter is pure acceleration, so the concepts of weight and passive gravitational mass do not exist. This suggests that Newton's second law might apply only to electromagnetic forces, and therefore inertial mass would be an electromagnetic magnitude. What we usually call 'weight' would be the manifestation of the upwards electromagnetic contact force that compensates gravitational acceleration when free fall is blocked by a material object. Since the electromagnetic force necessary to compensate a given gravitational acceleration would be proportional to inertial mass, this would explain why in practice inertial mass plays the role of passive gravitational mass.

GR makes other predictions incompatible with classical physics, like space-time

curvature, but these have never been proved experimentally. In principle, all experimental proofs of GR have been performed inside the domains $r > r_s$ for the propagation of radiation, and $r \gg r_s$ and $v \ll c$ for the effects on matter. Therefore, in principle the model seems compliant with all known GR tests.

6. Bell's inequality

Since our proposal is a local-realistic hidden-variables model, then, according to currently prevalent opinion, it should be considered incompatible with the Bell's inequality tests performed so far. However, Bell's theorem in its current form is not applicable to our model, because this theorem is based on a scheme where two 'objects', usually photons, depart from the same point, travel while remaining perfectly identifiable and equal to themselves, and are detected later at either some remote location A or another location B [9,10]. This applies in principle to all known Bell tests, including those published after 2015, which are theoretically loophole-free. Like Quantum theory, Bell's proof assumes that these objects remain immutable and fully identifiable from their emission to their detection, and that this detection is fully determined by the state of appropriate gates located near A and B respectively and with settings varying randomly. In other words, both Bell's proof and Quantum theory assume that photons are indivisible from their creation to their disappearance. However, in our model, particles may not necessarily be immutable or indivisible, or even exist at all: for example, in our model **there are no such things as free photons**. There may be events of the type '**photon emission**', when a transition between electronic levels causes a perturbation in the neighbouring field, but this perturbation may not result directly and univocally in a remote detection, because it may be diluted in the ether or combined with pre-existing perturbations. At the other end, there may be '**photon detection**' events, in which ether density locally reaches a level and pattern adequate to produce an electronic transition, but this event may not necessarily result from the arrival of something identifiable as a particle or photon. Instead, it may result, in all or part, from the accumulation of past perturbations arrived at different times. In general, in Bell tests, the succession of emissions globally causes a succession of detections, but individual emissions cannot be rigorously traced to individual detections one by one.

In principle, it should be possible to devise experiments locally forcing vacuum to behave as a collection of individually identifiable objects, but this has not been achieved so far. Recent experiments have advanced in this direction [11,12], but, significantly, the Bell coefficient values they report are the lowest and therefore most favourable to local hidden-variable models of all Bell tests performed so far.

Anyway, to avoid misunderstandings, it should be realised that the term 'identifiable' should not be related here to the concept of 'interchangeability' characteristic of Bose-Einstein statistics, if only because we consider here a single photon or 'entity' and by definition statistics involve many entities. In this document, a photon is considered 'identifiable' if it can be neatly distinguished as a whole from (the rest of) its surrounding fields, as in Quantum theory.

The above considerations also apply to the other well-known experiments at the origin of Quantum theory. For example, in the **double-slit experiment**, each 'photon emission' event produces a wave that travels through both slits simultaneously and interferes with itself, but does not necessarily produce a photon detection event at its arrival on the detection plate. However, after a few emissions, detection events will begin to occur and, statistically, they will occur most frequently on the maxima of the interference figure.

In **black-body cavities**, the ‘photon emission’ and ‘photon detection’ events occur at the walls of the chamber like in Quantum theory, therefore with the same consequences in terms of quantization, but what fills the cavity is radiation.

7. Other correspondences

The model can be made compatible, in principle, with all aspects of physics not mentioned so far, by adjusting the parts of the model that have been left open. It might be difficult to define realistic laws for this purpose, but it will certainly be possible to define theoretically suitable laws by including as many ad-hoc assumptions as necessary. The resulting model would still prove that the supposed experimental support provided by Bell tests for some controversial features of Quantum theory is at best dubious.

Additional indications about correspondences of the model with diverse physical entities are provided below.

Electrostatic interaction may result from the advance or delay of material events in the target object caused by the contribution of the field of the source charge to threshold effects at these points. This would imply that density excess would correspond to charges of some sign and density default to the other sign. This also implies that electromagnetic interaction is statistical by nature and explains the success of quantum electrodynamics, which is also statistical. As for the **magnetic force**, the mechanism seems somewhat more complicated. Further explanations are given in section 8.4.

Formulas like $E = mc^2$ and $E = hc/\lambda$ remain valid if λ is Compton’s wavelength for material particles and radiation wavelength for ‘photon emission’ and ‘photon detection’ events.

There are **no black holes**, but there might be very massive objects causing intense deflection or even total blockage of light rays.

There are no such things as Lorentz transformation proper, **space-time as a real object let alone curved, superposition of states, entanglement, gravitons or ‘strings’**.

Fine structure constant (α): because Compton’s wavelength is comprised $1/\alpha$ times inside the electronic orbit of the hydrogen atom ground state, $1/\alpha$ should be very close to an integer number, which it is ($1/\alpha \sim 137.036$). The reason why it is not an exact integer is probably that the Bohr model assumes that the radius of the orbit of the point equivalent to the electron in terms of mass is the same as the equivalent in terms of charge, which may not necessarily be exact in our model.

An **elementary particle** is a single uniformly spaced network of material points. The diversity of particles would result from that of the resonance frequencies of the ether.

The ‘material points’ might be what is detected inside hadrons in high-energy experiments as dense point-like objects and identified as **quarks**. This would explain why **free quarks** have never been observed.

The **strong interaction** could result from the intertwining of material point networks, which would explain its short range.

Strangeness, charm, isospin, hypercharge may be geometric properties of material networks, which we will not try to elucidate here, but they might also be just conventional ad-hoc nomenclature.

The model does not predict **weak interaction, neutrinos, or W, Z or Higgs bosons**, but it seems compatible with them, at least to some degree. According to our model and the experimental data, it seems clear that the **weak interaction** reflects a deep extensive restructuring of material structures, with change of internal spacing. **Neutrinos** could be pure torsions or whirls of vacuum, in which case they would have no mass, but, since they carry energy, they should contain something like a wave packet, or at least one peak of ether density whose width would reflect the energy load. In this aspect, they would be

similar to photons, and probably also in that they presumably do not exist as free individual identifiable particles, as already discussed for photons in the section about Bell tests and wave-particle duality. As for the **W and Z bosons**, they do not have a clear place or role in our model. According to the experiments performed so far and interpreted according to today's quantum physics, these particles have a life span around $2 \cdot 10^{-24}$ s and therefore a spatial range $< 10^{-15}$ m. In principle, this suggests that it is unlikely, though perhaps not impossible, that they play a central role in the restructuration of hadronic structures with a spacing of this order or greater, let alone in muonic or electronic networks several orders of magnitude bigger. With respect to the **Higgs boson**, according to our model it could reflect some resonance of the ether, but in no way it would confer mass, which is defined in our model, at least in its passive variant, by the material points and their spacing.

A further clue about the role of particles like photons or neutrinos in interactions may be deduced from the fact that, since De Broglie's wave is a phase wave faster than light, it cannot exist without a previously existing, possibly incoming structure, which therefore would be required at least for all reactions where fast particles are emitted by quasi-static objects. This point, though interesting, will not be further developed here because of its complexity.

8. Open aspects

8.1 High-precision experiments

This article leaves open the details of the wave propagation equation(s) or function(s), which are not necessary to establish the most significant results in terms of basic correspondences of this model with today's theoretical physics. Another reason why this analysis has been omitted is that most of its aspects seem exceedingly complex, probably requiring the collective work of teams of high-level specialists of statistical and field physics. In consequence, the model as presented here cannot account for the results of quantum (very)-high-precision experiments.

8.2 Orientation and combination of velocities. Safe speed limits

This article omits the calculations corresponding to velocities relative to ether that are not collinear with one of the axes of the material structure, because these calculations are relatively simple and devoid of interest.

In contrast, the superposition of the velocities of the material points relative to the material structure with a collective movement of this structure relative to the ether can be critical. Although a detailed calculation of this aspect would be very complicated, in a first approximation it seems clear that, according to our model, in matter travelling near the speed of light the material points would hardly have enough time to appear and therefore the particle would behave essentially as a wave. The problem is that these material points are essential to form atoms and molecules. In this respect, if we take as reference the hydrogen atom, where, according to our model, the electron travels at a speed of $c / 137$, it seems clear that, if the whole atom travels around this speed or faster, its group velocity could interfere with that of the interactions exchanged by the material points, destroying the synchronism of the structure and causing it to disintegrate. More precisely, some material points could be formed by the convergence of interactions generated by other material points formed at the wrong locations. When returning to much lower speeds, it

is likely that simple atoms or molecules could reconstruct themselves without problem, but this would probably be impossible for macromolecules, which therefore would be irreversibly denatured.

A possible relatively safe speed limit would have to be several times lower than $c / 137$, for example $c / 300$ at most. This represents about 1000 km/s, which can be compared, for example, with Earth's escape velocity of 11.2 km/s, Earth's velocity relative to the Sun of ~ 30 km/s, or typical galaxy rotation speeds of 100 - 300 km/s. These examples seem to show that these speed ranges are safe in principle, but what may happen above ~ 1000 km/s is unclear and we had better test it first with inert objects before trying to make live beings travel at these speeds. It should also be noted that if, as hypothesized by today's predominantly accepted scientific cosmology, there is an expansion of the universe with creation of vacuum (of ether in our model), then the above restrictions would not apply to the recession speed of remote galaxies, because they apply to the speed relative to local ether, and for the same reason, in our model, this recession speed would imply no cosmologically significant time dilation proper.

8.3 Structure of protons and other hadrons

In principle, the available experimental data suggest that the dimension of the material part of the proton is of the same order as its Compton wavelength, that is, ~ 1.32 fm ($1.32 \cdot 10^{-15}$ m) [13]. This would imply that the material part of a proton contains just a few material points, perhaps only 3.

It has not been possible for the author to devise a clean and precise arrangement of 3 or a few more point-like material points fulfilling the above conditions without ad-hoc assumptions. This does not mean that such arrangement does not exist, but it could also happen that at this scale the volume of the material points and the duration of the material events becomes significant. In particular, the simplest model with spin that the author has been able to devise, based on a regular hexagon with 6 material points, does not seem possible without taking into account the volume and duration of the material points and events. The resulting distortions of the direction and speed of the interactions might have the same cause as those occurring in gravitational fields, as explained in the section about GR. This could explain why the proton is the only stable hadron observed so far: its dimensions might be an optimal fit for those of its material points. It has been necessary also to assume that the value of 1.32 fm currently accepted for the Compton wavelength of the proton corresponds approximately to the length of the main diagonal of the hexagon instead of its edge. Additionally, the model of proton presented here is based, at least in a first attempt, on the currently accepted values of ~ 0.84 - 0.85 fm for the proton 'effective' (rms) electric/magnetic radius [14], about the same for the minimum separation between nucleons at zero strong force, and a radial coordinate of ~ 2 fm for the maximum effective range of the strong force [15]. The proposed model is represented in Figure 4 and provides a reasonable agreement with experimental values, considering that it is the policy of the author to avoid making assumptions too obviously ad-hoc.

Figure 4 - Possible structure of the proton

The figure represents a hypothetical structure of the proton comprising 6 material points. The numbers near the material points represent, in arbitrary units of time, the instants (time coordinates) of their material events. The arrows represent the interactions coinciding at each point. Interactions not likely to reach the material event threshold have not been represented. In the drawing (a), all the interactions satisfying this condition are represented. In (b), for clarity, only the interactions coinciding at the material point marked {3 - 9} are represented. The drawing (c) represents the same interactions as (b), but it also shows a hypothetical range / volume for the material points and their intensities at about time ~ 1.5 , with darker colors for greater intensities. Logically, the material points at 1-7 and 2-8 have the greatest intensities, and those at 4-10 and 5-11 the lowest. The real material points probably do not have a clear frontier, but a density gradient. The rotation of the material events at these points is what generates the spin of the proton. The purpose of the colors in the figure is to enhance visibility; they are not intended to represent the concept of ‘color’ of quarks proposed by today’s Quantum Chromodynamics (QCD). In our model, strong interaction takes place between hadrons, not quarks, and probably results from the intertwining of their rings, as represented in view (d1) (bound) and (d2) (free).

A similar model is possible with a regular pentagon, heptagon, etc. With a square, it seems already possible, but unlikely, and it does not seem to fit into a triangle without important changes, like a substantial use of field lines. On the other hand, one reason why the hexagon was chosen is that, although the reconciliation of our theory with the quark model is hopeless, it seems prudent, *ceteris paribus*, to propose a model with fractional charges compatible with those of the quark model, just in case.

In order to verify the validity and the (im)precision of the model, we can use it to calculate the magnetic moment of the proton, whose experimental value is $\sim 1.41 \cdot 10^{-26}$ J/T [14]. We use the classical formula, initially with a linear rotation speed $\sim c$ and a radius of 0.84 fm. We obtain $2.02 \cdot 10^{-26}$ J/T, which is a good start but not the precise experimental value, so the model must be adjusted. We can note that this discrepancy also affects similar models based on pentagons, heptagons, etc. In all these cases, it seems reasonable to assume that the real effective linear rotation speed is somewhat lower than c , but it is difficult to guess by what factor. A speed of $0.7 c$ would make a very good agreement, and the model also tolerates somewhat higher speeds if we diminish the radius within a range $> \sim 0.6$ fm, which does not seem unreasonable if we consider that what is currently known as the proton electric / magnetic ‘radius’ is not a geometric measurable concept, but the result of a complicated abstract quantum-mechanical calculation [16]. We can also hypothesize some phenomenon affecting the electric field, such as some degree of obliquity or directionality in the field lines. There could be many other possibilities, like the presence of full or ‘partial’ material points at the centre or at lower radii. However, to avoid the temptation of cluttering and denaturing the model with ad-hoc features, we will leave it open within the ranges explained above. In any case, the model as presented here can serve at least as a basis or reference for future research.

As for the neutron, the available experimental evidence suggests that its most probable structure is composed of a proton at the centre surrounded by negative material points. The comparison between the magnetic moments of the proton ($1.41 \cdot 10^{-26}$ J/T) and the neutron ($-0.966 \cdot 10^{-26}$ J/T [14]) is a strong indication that the neutron consists of a proton surrounded by an equivalent negative charge, coplanar and roughly toroidal, with a magnetic moment $\sim -2.38 \cdot 10^{-26}$ J/T. Of the two different material structures already discussed in this article, in principle we can exclude the leptonic one, which would imply an attraction of electromagnetic nature because of the difference between leptonic and protonic structures, so the negative charge could be dislodged by electromagnetic interaction. In addition, this arrangement would imply either an excessive mass of the negative charge if located near the proton, or a distance of the order of the Bohr radius if we take into account the measured difference between the masses of the proton and neutron, which is of the order of 2.5 times the mass of the electron [14], or a combination of both problems. By contrast, if we consider a structure more similar to that of our model of proton, and integrated with it, with a common mass and Compton wavelength, the negative part would have a radius of $\sqrt{(-\mu_N + \mu_P) / \mu_P} \sim 1.298$ times that of the proton. This would imply that, if the rotation speed of the proton is close to that of light, the negative part would rotate faster than light, but this is not a problem, because in our model each negative material point is not generated by its negative predecessor, but by a point of the proton. In other words, the succession of the material events in the negative material points forms a phase wave. The resulting model of neutron, based on a hexagon like that of the proton, is represented in Figure 5. The generalization of this structure to other neutral particles or to all sets of particles bound by weak interaction will be left open, but we can note that in general neutral particles are far less stable than their charged counterparts, presumably because neutral massive particles are always composed of two or more charged particles, which are more stable because of the homogeneity of their structure and the stabilizing effect of their electric field on their material point network.

Figure 5 - Possible structure of the neutron

The figure represents a hypothetical structure of the neutron, composed of a proton made of 6 material points with positive charge, surrounded in the same plane by 6 other material points negatively charged. The figure derives from Fig. 4c and follows the same conventions with respect to the interactions represented as arrows, and also for the times, in arbitrary units of time, of the material events occurring at the material points. For clarity, only the interactions already represented for the proton and those converging at the two negative material points marked {2 - 8} and {3 - 9} have been represented. This arrangement is in good agreement with the experimental value of the ratio between the magnetic moments of the proton and the neutron.

Further indications about the differences between leptons and hadrons can be deduced from the properties measured so far for the tau lepton, as compared with a typical hadron, the proton, which has about half the mass of the former. The gyromagnetic ratio deduced for the tau from experiments is very close to that of the electron and muon [14], which is a strong indication that the material structures of these particles are very similar, with a cubic arrangement as described above for the electron. As a consequence, the tau would tend to form toroidal structures, with a radius in inverse proportion to its mass relative to the electron mass and the Bohr radius, that is, around $1.5 \cdot 10^{-14} \text{ m} = 15 \text{ fm}$. By contrast, the gyromagnetic ratio of the proton is clearly different, suggesting a very different structure, as outlined before and sketched in Figure 4.

8.4 Mechanism of electromagnetic interaction

We will assume that **electrostatic interaction** results from the influence of the ether density field produced by the source charge on the material points of the target charge. This implies that we identify ether density with electric potential, with the appropriate

choice of units, and that ether density excess corresponds to charges of some sign and ether density default to the other sign. According to the mechanism of material points, if for example we have a small positive charge Q_2 inside a zone where the electric potential diminishes radially from another small positive charge Q_1 , the material points of Q_2 located closer to Q_1 will reach their threshold more frequently than those located farther from Q_1 , which, according to our model, should accelerate Q_2 away from Q_1 . This example illustrates the repulsion between charges of same sign and, more generally, this view is fully compatible with the classical formulas $\vec{E} = -\overline{\text{grad}} V$ and $\vec{F} = Q\vec{E}$. This also implies that electromagnetic interaction is statistical by nature and explains, at least in part, the success of quantum electrodynamics, which is also statistical.

Undulations of the electromagnetic potential at the scale of material points, at the edge of a wire. **(a)** Immobile charges, electrostatic field. All the material points are synchronized. **(b)** With current. The material points move towards the right and fire in sequence. In both pictures, the green and orange wavelets are simultaneous but generated in different cycles. \vec{A} is the magnetic vector potential. The vectors $\vec{\Sigma}$ and \vec{E} have no physical effect: they are associated to the electric field, but none of them represents this field. These vectors represent the velocity of the undulations of the electric potential at the scale of material points, whereas the electric field is generated by the gradient of this potential. Furthermore, the electric field of these vectors is compensated by that of charges of opposite sign of the wire, but this is very difficult to represent on a picture because this compensation is not exact at the material point scale, but only on average at the particle scale.

Figure 6 – Effect of the motion of charge on its surrounding electric potential

For the **magnetic interaction**, we will assume that the **magnetic vector potential** produced by a moving charge represents the projection, on the direction of the velocity of the charge, of the velocity of the undulations of the electric potential produced by the activity of the material points of this charge.

Figure 6 gives a simplified view of the mechanism by which the motion of electric charge inside a conductor affects the circulation of the undulations of electric potential caused by the material points of these charges outside their spatial domain.

In principle, our assumption seems compatible with the postulates of classical electromagnetism, if only because our model already assumes that, in the domain of linear propagation, the waves of electric potential follow the rules of classical electromagnetism. We can also note that, according to this assumption, the real physical phenomenon underlying magnetism is the magnetic vector potential \vec{A} , whereas we establish by definition that the magnetic field $\vec{B} = \overline{curl}\vec{A}$, as in Maxwell's equation. Unfortunately, it does not seem possible in practice to deduce from our model the whole of classical electromagnetism, given the enormous variety of possible geometric configurations, and also because this would require in principle a complete definition of the combined linear + nonlinear propagation law of our model. Therefore, we will limit our explanation to a single example: we will compare the predictions of our model with the formulas of classical electromagnetism corresponding to the magnetic attraction between two very long parallel wires. This example has two advantages: its formulas are relatively simple, and they exist for the magnetic force between two long wires as well as for the electrostatic force between two long linear charges.

The mechanism of magnetic interaction for two parallel wires is explained in Fig. 7: the curl of the magnetic potential produced by one of the wires is 'seen' by a charge travelling inside the other wire with a different Doppler effect at each of its sides. More precisely, if the two currents have the same sign and direction, because of the Doppler effect the moving charge encounters, per unit of time, less undulations at its side closer to the other wire than at its opposite side. Therefore, this opposite side experiences more threshold-crossing events than the side closer to the other wire, producing an acceleration towards this wire, because of the mechanism of material points described in previous sections, and in agreement with classical magnetism.

In order to verify our mechanism quantitatively, we note that its magnitude is proportional to the speeds of the charges inside their respective wires, and that its maximum magnitude, equivalent to electrostatic interaction, occurs when both speeds are arbitrarily close to c . Therefore, using as reference the formula of the electrostatic force F_e between two long linear parallel charges of length L

$$\frac{F_e}{L} = \frac{q_1 q_2}{2\pi\epsilon_0 r} ,$$

where q_1 and q_2 are the linear charge densities respectively inside the linear charges 1 and 2, and r is the distance between these linear charges, we write the formula of the magnetic force F_m between two long wires with currents I_1 and I_2 by multiplying the electrostatic formula by v_1/c and v_2/c , where v_1 and v_2 are the velocities of the charges respectively inside the wires 1 and 2:

$$\frac{F_m}{L} = \frac{q_1 v_1 q_2 v_2}{2\pi\epsilon_0 c^2 r} = \frac{\mu_0 I_1 I_2}{2\pi r} ,$$

which is the formula of classical electromagnetism.

Figure 7 – Mechanism of the magnetic attraction between two parallel wires

(a): Electric potential produced by a linear immobile negative charge, in accordance to Fig 6 (a) with opposite sign. (b): Potential produced by a current of negative charges, as in Fig. 6 (b) but with opposite sign. This picture is also applicable to the electron represented in Fig. 2. (c): Potential produced by a current of positive charges, as in Fig. 6 (b). (d) and (e): Effect of the magnetic field produced by a current I_1 on a small parallelepipedal charge of a parallel wire 2 with current I_2 . Because of the curl of the magnetic vector potential \vec{A} , the travelling charge is subject to a different Doppler effect at each of its sides, and therefore it ‘sees’ more electric potential undulations at its right than at its left. In consequence, its material points experience more threshold-crossing events on its right, which produces, according to our material point model, an acceleration towards the left, amounting to an attraction force, in accordance with the rules of classical electromagnetism applicable to the magnetic field \vec{B} and the magnetic force \vec{F} .

We will now briefly justify the full equation

$$\vec{E} = -\overrightarrow{\text{grad}} V - \frac{\partial \vec{A}}{\partial t},$$

where the first term of the second member has already been justified and the second term represents the **electromagnetic induction**. Let us imagine for example two consecutive material points P_1 and P_2 located in this order from left to right on a horizontal line inside a positive charge where the magnetic potential \vec{A} points towards the right and increases with time. The point P_1 initiates a cycle at a certain instant, and by the time this cycle reaches P_2 , the increase of electric potential at this scale caused by the increase of \vec{A} will cause P_2 to reach its threshold sooner than if there had been no net transfer of electric potential, therefore inducing an acceleration of the couple in the direction $P_2 \rightarrow P_1$, like an electrostatic field oriented in this direction and in accordance with the above equation. Whether this influence can be considered an electric field proper is a question of nomenclature open to debate, but it certainly influences charges like an electrostatic field and therefore in principle can be regarded as an alternative form of electric field, at least on average at the scale of particles, and it can create differences of electric potential through its effect on charged particles.

9. The value of the high-precision ‘predictions’ of QED

The model presented here is clearly incompatible with the formalism of Quantum Field Theories (QFT) and in particular with Quantum Electrodynamics (QED). However, it is well known that these theories sometimes (though not always) reproduce experimental results with enormous precision, which is often considered an indication, if not a proof, that these theories are realistic and accurate. However, as we shall explain below, an in-depth analysis shows that, in this domain, things are not as direct and intuitive as they may seem at first sight.

9.1 *Ad-hoc aspects*

In the first place, it is fundamental to point out that the mere fact of ‘predicting’ an experimental result with utmost precision may mean nothing. Let us suppose, for example, that for a certain magnitude our theory predicts a value of 1 and the experimental result is 2.00112245. To ‘improve’ the precision of our theory, we just need to modify it by adding to our previous result a constant 1.00112245. This proves that, in itself, the extreme precision of any theoretical result is worth nothing unless the degree of ‘ad-hocness’ of the theory is not significant. Of course, the ad-hoc tricks may be performed in a far less simplistic way: for example, one can define different constants for the different physical entities dealt with by the theory, and apply these constants automatically by means of something like ‘if/else’ clauses or matrices with many zeroes. It is also possible to define parametrized formulas and fine-tune their parameters so as to match the experimental results with the maximum possible precision. However, a reasonably detailed analysis of the different QFTs of today’s theoretical physics appears to show that the use of such methods in these theories is not evident, for which reason it would be useless to reproduce this analysis here. Instead, it would seem that the essential ad-hoc aspect of these theories is the entire formalism of the theory itself; after all, in principle, there is no reason why ad-hoc features should always be simplistic and consist merely in adding, or multiplying by, a simple constant. However, when the full theory seems ad-hoc in block, one may wonder whether the accuracy of its ‘predictions’ can legitimate this theory in full. This point is analysed for QFTs in the following section.

9.2 Statistical magnitudes

It is well known that, in physical statistical theories, precise results or ‘predictions’ can be obtained with rather rudimentary models of the individual physical entities. For example, the kinetic theory of ideal gases provides formulas like $PV = NRT$, reasonably accurate at low densities and high temperatures, on the basis of a rather rudimentary model of molecule. This theory cannot, however, predict phenomena like phase transitions, but this can be achieved by including a rudimentary parametrised intermolecular radial interaction potential [17], and in this way we could be able to reproduce with reasonable precision phenomena like phase transitions. However, even this improved model will still be completely unable to reproduce the chemical and nuclear properties of the substances, for which purpose we would need to modify it again, and so on. In sum, precise values for some statistical physical magnitudes can be obtained by using different models for the individual entities, including very rudimentary ones.

There can be little doubt that QFTs are statistical theories, because they are mainly intended to predict statistical magnitudes, such as cross sections and decay times, and also because significant similarities between QFT and statistical mechanics have already been pointed out [18]. On the other hand, the model of electrical interaction presented here is also statistical. In consequence, there seems to be nothing extraordinary in that QFTs, and especially QED, could be able to reproduce with enormous precision the experimental values of some statistical physical magnitudes while being radically unable to reproduce, calculate or predict other important physical phenomena, and with all the more reason if these phenomena are not of statistical nature, like superposition of states or entanglement. Further details on this subject are given in the next section.

9.3 The ‘anomalous’ magnetic moment of the electron

The most impressive achievement of any known QFT, by far, has been the calculation or prediction by QED of the so-called ‘anomalous magnetic moment’ of the electron with a (claimed) coincidence of up to around 12 decimal places with the experimental value. We will not perform here any critical evaluation of this achievement, but instead we will calculate the predictions of our model about this same subject and try to extract useful conclusions from our results.

The expressions ‘anomalous magnetic moment of the electron’ or ‘correction to the magnetic moment of the electron’ refer to the small difference between the predicted or experimental values of this moment and the value of the Bohr magneton, which corresponds to the magnetic moment of a charge e describing a circle of radius a_0 , the Bohr radius, at linear speed $c\alpha$, where α is the fine-structure constant $\approx 1/137.06$.

Given the structure that we have postulated for the electron of the hydrogen atom and sketched in Fig. 2, we will try to evaluate the influence on the magnetic moment of the distribution of the charge of the electron along several concentric circles. The magnetic moment of each of these circles is proportional to $I.r^2$, where the current I can be considered identical for all of these circles and r is the radius of the circle. We will estimate the total magnetic moment of a few coplanar concentric currents of radius $\approx a_0$ separated by the Compton wavelength of the electron λ_c and of common intensity, by developing r^2 as $a_0(1 + \varepsilon)^2 = a_0(1 + 2\varepsilon + \varepsilon^2)$, where $\varepsilon = \lambda_c / a_0 = 2\pi\alpha$.

We obtain the following relative corrections:

- For 3 concentric circles, with respective radii $a_0(1 - \varepsilon)$, a_0 and $a_0(1 + \varepsilon)$, the relative correction is ≈ 0.001401 .

- For 2 concentric circles, with radii $a_0 (1 - \varepsilon/2)$ and $a_0 (1 + \varepsilon/2)$, the relative correction is ≈ 0.000526 .

Since the experimental value is 0.001159562, we can easily deduce that our model of electron must be something intermediate between these two arrangements of concentric circles. A simple combination of these two arrangements, with 5 circles, results in a correction ≈ 0.00105 , and with two additional circles of less intensity the result can be very close to the experimental value. We can also add circles in parallel planes, in which case the total relative contribution, with good precision, would be the average of the different planes. This arrangement has been represented in Fig.8, which can be considered an improvement on Fig.2 based on the reference of the magnetic moment.

- (a): Assembly of 5 circular coplanar concentric currents of same intensity I , equivalent in total to the rotation of the electronic charge of the Bohr atom. The difference between the theoretical magnetic moment \vec{m} of this simple structure and the Bohr magneton is comparable to the difference measured for real electrons and the QED value.
- (b): Three-dimensional view of an electron, as in Fig.2, and its magnetic moment \vec{m}_e . In this view, the planes of concentric circles of material points have not been represented in detail.
- (c): Detail of the arrangement and intensity of the material points of an electron inside its middle plane, viewed from the direction of \vec{m}_e . Unlike Fig.2, this picture uses the shades of grey to represent mostly the postulated intensity of the material points instead of their likeliness, the material points that have been represented are those that reach the same extremum of their cycle approximately at the same time, and the spacing equivalent to the Compton wavelength of the electron λ_c has been indicated in the figure at several places.

Figure 8 – Magnetic moment produced by the material points of a stationary electron

It seems evident that we could adjust the distribution, size and intensity of our material points so as to match the experimental value of the magnetic moment correction up to any number of decimals, but we will abstain from doing that because it could be considered an ad-hoc procedure, and also because there are presumably infinitely many forms of doing that, which should be later checked against many other experimental results. However, it is already remarkable that our prediction matches the experimental value up to 4 decimal digits not only without any ad-hoc assumption, but as an inevitable consequence of the properties of our model.

Discussion

Probably the most surprising aspect of the above calculation is the absolute incompatibility between the methods used respectively in QED and in our model to obtain the same numeric result: suffice it to note that the QED correction is of order α , whereas that of our model is of order α^2 , a discrepancy compensated by the fact that $\alpha/2\pi$ happens to be very close to $2\pi^2\alpha^2$. Even the author was surprised by this radical incompatibility, after having always tried to complete the basic model proposed in this document with a calculation much closer to the QED postulates than the one explained here, and then realizing that QED and our model obtain the same numeric result in completely different ways impossible to reconcile with each other at the theoretical level. In a few words, QED and more generally QFTs describe as physical events occurring in the fields surrounding material particles the same physical phenomena that our model describes as consequences of the structure of matter beyond the scale of what is known in today's physics as elementary particles. In other words, despite their name, QFTs are not field theories but theories about the structure of matter. However, a deeper analysis shows that this treatment is not new and seems a consequence of our past ignorance of the internal structure of 'elementary' particles: much for the same reason, Special Relativity 'transferred' the Lorentz length contraction and time dilation from the structure of matter to the surrounding space-time, and fundamental Quantum theory invented a strange kind of rotation incompatible with geometry, the 'spin', probably the only possible way of 'explaining' the presence of magnetic moment, and therefore rotation, in a supposedly non-orbiting particle considered essentially point-like in these times.

These considerations and the obvious incompatibility of the QFT formalism with physical realism seem to confirm the idea, expressed in previous sections, that what is ad-hoc in such theories is the theory itself as a whole. Apparently, what seems to have occurred in the 20th century is that theoretical physicists developed QFTs essentially by trial and error, without much regard for the mathematical rigor and physical significance of the theoretical concepts that they invented. This could explain the considerable proliferation of QFTs and also their reported applicability to subjects very different from particle physics, such as phase transitions and statistical mechanics in general. In this respect, it may be interesting to note that, whereas Special Relativity, General Relativity, basic Quantum theory, QFTs like QED, QCD or Electroweak theory, the Standard Model, and the profusion of GUTs and TOEs proposed so far are built on a heterogenous variety of ad-hoc postulates independent from each other, our proposal postulates a unified physically meaningful mechanism as a basis for the whole of theoretical physics.

We can also observe that, whereas Relativity and our model obtain similar formulas in incompatible ways, Quantum theories and our model apparently obtain the same numeric results from incompatible formulas. Since the second condition is clearly more difficult to fulfil consistently, this could explain why, whereas Relativity was developed essentially by a single person in a few years, it took a lot of people working for several decades to develop the full system of Quantum theories in vigour at present, and also why this system is clearly less mathematically rigorous and physically meaningful than Relativity. As for the reason of these differences, most probably there is no deeper explanation than that for quantum phenomena the task is simply much more difficult than for relativistic effects. This can also explain why, whereas several authors have already proposed ether theories of gravity and sometimes also hints of a model of SR resembling the one proposed here, but without detailing the structure of matter, nobody has ever been able to propose a clean complete theory for quantum phenomena (whereas the theory proposed here could be considered reasonably 'clean', its quantum high-precision part is not complete, though today's 'official' theories are not really complete either).

10. Decisive experiments

As with all new theoretical models, it is mandatory to propose experiments whose result could confirm or invalidate the new theory when compared to the pre-existing model that it intends to replace or improve. In our case, there would be at least the following.

10.1 Relativity

If an observer A travelling at relativistic speed with respect to another observer B sees that objects linked to B are shorter than at rest, and clocks slower, our model predicts that B will perceive that the objects linked to A are longer and faster. By contrast, SR predicts that B will also perceive A objects as shorter and slower, in proportion to the Lorentz factor in both cases. Any other result would invalidate SR down to its very foundations, and therefore also GR, theoretical relativistic cosmology, and the current QFT formalism, all of which is a necessary condition to confirm the model presented here. However, the full confirmation of this model would require in addition performing several tests with different orientations of the velocities of A and B relative to each other, and verifying that all the results are consistent with a single value of the local velocity of ether relative to independent reference observers not affected by the movements of A and B.

Please note that the author does not have enough knowledge of state-of-the-art technology to estimate whether such experiment is already possible or will be so in the near future, and at what cost. However, it seems clear that there is a profusion of possible ways to perform this test, for example in open space, in orbit or on Earth, with manned vehicles or unmanned devices, etc. In principle, the task of choosing the experiment(s) with the best reliability / cost ratio should be reserved to specialists of the different possible technologies. It would be very important, however, to take into account the possibility, described elsewhere in this document, of spontaneous disintegration or denaturation of macroscopic objects at speeds around 1000 km/s or more. In principle, exceeding the safety limit of ~300 km/s that can be deduced from astronomical observations should be considered not only dangerous for human observers, but also inappropriate for unmanned devices, because the instability of material structures at these speeds could cause the experimental apparatuses to malfunction.

10.2 Quantum theory

One such decisive experiment is already under way: unlike standard Quantum theory, our model predicts that quantum computers will never be able to achieve the exponential performance currently expected from them, because this performance would require features like superposition of states and quantum entanglement, which are incompatible with our model. After several years of countless unsuccessful attempts, this prediction seems to hold, because this level of performance has never been approached, even remotely. This failure is generally blamed now on some instability or lack of isolation that causes errors, but what our model suggests instead is that these 'errors' are simply the consequence of the random nature of individual photon or 'particle' emissions and detections, as explained in the section about Bell's theorem.

Unfortunately, as far as the author has been able to analyse, it does not seem easy to prove decisively that the reason of this failure is theoretical and not practical, short of continuing the ongoing research for several more years with the corresponding costs, unless some reader comes up with a clever idea for a definitive test on the matter. In principle, such proof would require tricky mathematics, and past experience has shown

that even the theoretical basis of a much simpler experiment, the Bell test, has been misunderstood by practically all relevant theoretical physicists for more than 60 years. Inversely, an eventual success of quantum computer technology as currently planned would invalidate the model presented here.

10.3 Stability of the sub-elementary structure of matter

The model presented here predicts that, at speeds around 2000-3000 km/s relative to ether, matter would disintegrate into pure waves. Therefore, a possible test of our model could consist in accelerating pieces of matter to speeds of, say, 3000 km/s or more, and verify whether they disintegrate or not. For this purpose, it would be necessary to use material objects with a very low probability of reassembling themselves spontaneously after disintegration. Therefore, in principle atoms are excluded, and small molecules might not be easily predictable, so these experiments should use macroscopic objects or at least macromolecules with many possible stable forms.

In principle, any reliable observation of such objects travelling relative to ether at speeds around 2000-4000 km/s or more, without falling apart or being denatured, would invalidate the model presented here. Since the local velocity of ether might not be known a priori, many observations with different orientations of velocities with respect to independent reference observers should be performed. Inversely, the disintegration of macroscopic matter at speeds around 1000 to 3000 km/s would be a strong argument in favour of our model, although, above this speed range, the higher the disintegration speed, the weaker the argument in favour of our model.

As in the case of the SR length contraction / time dilation test, there are many possible experimental setups, whose choice should be left to specialists of the different possible technologies. Of course, for obvious reasons, the material objects accelerated to speeds within the abovementioned ranges should always be unmanned.

11. Compatibility with the high-precision results of QED

In this section, we will not discuss the capacity of our model to reproduce the high-precision results of today's Quantum Electrodynamics (QED). This point has already been left open because of its complexity, and it will remain so for now. Instead, what will be discussed here is the compatibility of the present QED results with the Special Relativity part of our new model. We have already shown that the precision of the QED results could be explained by noting that this theory is of statistical nature, at least in its quantum aspects, and one of the basic assumptions of our model is that all probabilistic phenomena have an underlying deterministic mechanism, perhaps very complicated but real. However, Quantum Field Theories (QFT) are based not only on the Quantum formalism, but also on Special Relativity, which is not a statistical theory, and whose formulation in the new model is significantly different from that of Einstein, so it seems reasonable to investigate in detail the compatibility of today's QED with our new model.

In this model, the Lorentz factors derive from the velocity of the observed objects relative to ether, whereas in Einstein's relativity they derive from the velocity of these objects relative to the observer. Furthermore, in our model it is matter that shrinks and clocks which run more slowly, whereas in the original Special Relativity it is the whole space or time dimension that is transformed. Therefore, in our analysis, in principle the first step should be the determination of the velocity of the observers relative to ether. For this purpose, we will choose a value $v_e \sim 300$ km/s, whose order of magnitude seems to correspond to the linear rotation velocity at the edge of the galaxy [19], and this particular

value is convenient because it amounts approximately to $c/1000$. If we suppose that there is some ether drag at the edge of the galaxy, or we think that the current estimations of the rotation speed of the galaxy are wrong, then the next obvious choice will be $v_e \sim 30$ km/s $\sim c/10000$, the speed of Earth in its orbit around the Sun.

For $v_e \sim 300$ km/s, the precision of the Lorentz factor is $\gamma - 1 \sim 10^{-6}$, which seems more than sufficient for all practical applications. Unfortunately, a much higher precision has been claimed for some QED results: around 10^{-10} or even 10^{-12} [20, 21]. This degree of precision has no practical use except for annoying the inventors of new theories, but it has been trumpeted almost obsessively for decades, so it seems almost mandatory to verify that these ultraprecise results are compatible with a real world described by the SR of our model instead of that of Einstein.

A possible mechanism guaranteeing this compatibility is the effect of Lorentz length contraction and time dilation on the observation instruments. In simple terms, if an observer measures a distance of, say, 10 m, with a ruler measuring 1 m, and then this ruler magically shrinks to 80 cm, but the distance of 10 m also shrinks to 8 m, the observer will still measure a distance of 10 m. In our theory, both effects would result from the movement of the laboratory relative to ether. Furthermore, this correspondence is likely to be exact, at least for the following reasons: first, because it is analogous to the transformation resulting from a change of units of measure, which is exact; second, because in practice this is what happens in the Michelson-Morley experiment, as explained before: because of the contraction of the longitudinal arm of the apparatus, this experiment does not detect the least trace of ether movement, at whatever degree of precision. Therefore, in principle it seems that we can assume that even the most precise results of QED are compatible with our model, but only as long as the following conditions are satisfied:

- In the QED view of the experiment, the relativistic effects result only from the movement of the objects under observation relative to the laboratory, not directly from the movement of these objects relative to each other.
- The experiment measures only space and time intervals between locations and events related or connected by material structures or chains of cause-effect events. Otherwise, the Lorentz effects of our model would not apply to the voids separating these space-time events.

The above conditions apply in principle to fully equipped, macroscopic observers, that is, for the group of low-energy, high-precision QED experiments, but it seems less clear whether they are also valid for the high-energy group of experiments, essentially scattering experiments in which the particles of interest are not ‘measured’ by a macroscopic apparatus, but by other particles participating in the experiment. Our model has its own composition law for velocities, but it is not exactly equivalent to that of SR, so according to our model the extreme precision of low-energy QED experiments cannot be guaranteed for high-energy experiments. Furthermore, in these experiments the velocities that are usually taken into account are relative to the centre of mass, which may not necessarily coincide with the laboratory frame with a precision of the order of 10^{-10} or more. We will not attempt here to determine the exact influence of the Lorentz effect on a collision between particles, which in our model could be extremely complicated, so in principle we will admit that there is apparently no objective reason to suppose that the precision of the QED description of scattering experiments is limited by factors related to SR, but also that there is no lack of factors that could limit it. Anyway, the fact is that in practice the precision of these QED experiments is several orders of magnitude lower than that of ‘low energy’ QED experiments, which is compatible with the above analysis. Furthermore, there could be other factors limiting the precision of the ‘high-energy’

experiments, but related, this time, to quantum phenomena instead of SR considerations: the complicated internal structure of matter particles postulated in our model, which is ‘visible’ in principle only to ‘high-energy’ experiments, is clearly different from the view of today’s quantum theories, in which elementary particles are just point-like objects with non-geometric intrinsic properties. Unfortunately, it seems very complicated to calculate the imprecision that could result from this simplification, but we may have an interesting indication: as noted before, in our model the fine-structure constant should be in principle an exact inverse integer, but the value used in today’s physics is not: the currently accepted value is $1/\alpha \sim 137.036$. This represents an imprecision between 10^{-3} and 10^{-4} , which is comparable to that of ‘high energy’ QED experiments. We can also note that this difference between $1/\alpha$ and 137 cannot result only from replacing a 137-sided regular polygon by its inscribed or circumscribed circle.

In sum, the above analysis provides the following interesting conclusions:

- First of all, it provides a possible mechanism for the compatibility of our model with the predictions and results of today’s quantum field theories, including QED, regardless of their precision.

- It provides a possible explanation for the considerable differences of precision between the diverse QED and QFT predictions and experiments.

- It explains how, in practice, a model of SR where only material objects are directly affected by relativistic phenomena can expand its reach to observations of the whole space and time dimensions, as in the original SR.

- It confirms that, in principle, QED/QFT-type experiments are not adequate to confirm or disprove the model presented here. As explained in a previous section, for this purpose a truly decisive experiment would require at least two fully equipped observers travelling relative to each other at a speed high enough to produce clearly detectable relativistic effects.

- It provides some indications on whether today’s quantum field theories could still be used as ‘effective theories’ if the model presented here happened to be confirmed by experiments. In sum, it would seem that this use would likely be more problematic than it is now for, say, Newtonian mechanics or Maxwell’s electromagnetism.

12. Appendix. Detailed description of the electron of the hydrogen atom in the ground state

The explanations of this section are based on Figure 9, in which the main picture (a) represents at a given instant t_0 the structure and state of the middle plane of an electron in the ground state of the hydrogen atom, outlined in light blue, with all the material points of its middle circle, and a sample of the material points of its other 4 main circles. As explained in sections 2, 3, 4 and 9.3, this plane comprises 5 main circles composed each of 137 material points separated by a distance equal to the Compton wavelength of the electron λ_e , intercalated with another set of 137 material points in opposite phase. Around the electron, the figure represents the phases, at 8 of its locations, of the corresponding material points of one of these sets, conventionally represented in dark blue, the points of the other set being represented in orange. The phases are indicated by the level of the electric potential V at the point, represented inside a vertical rectangle showing the maximum and minimum values reached by the oscillation of electric potential at the material points. For the locations A, B, C, D and E, separate frames represent the detail of the phases of material points of each of the two abovementioned sets.

Figure 9 – Detail of the structure of the electron in the hydrogen atom ground state

In the entire section, if not stated otherwise, the word ‘cycle’ will be used to designate two apparently different things that are in fact the same in the fundamental electronic state: the cycle or period of De Broglie’s wave, and the cycle or period of the oscillation of the ether density (= electric potential) at a material point between a maximum and a minimum. It should be noted that, although the period of De Broglie’s wave and that of the material points is the same, the corresponding distances are very different, because De Broglie’s wave is much faster: its wavelength is 137 times greater than that of the oscillation of the material points, which is the Compton wavelength. As for the rotation of the electron along its orbit, it is still much slower: it takes 137^2 of the aforementioned cycles for the electron to achieve a complete rotation along its orbit. The following explanations refer to the phases of the different objects inside their associated cycles.

For example, we can note that at instant t_0 the ‘dark’ point at B is $1/8$ cycle late with respect to its equivalent at A because, as explained in sections 3 and 4, if the electron rotates clockwise, the point at A must be $1/8$ cycle in advance of the point at B. For this reason, the point at B will reach its maximum at t_1 , $1/8$ cycle later than the point at A. We can also note that this figure shows why for a stationary state in which the electron travels along a circular trajectory at uniform speed the length of the orbit must be an exact multiple of De Broglie’s wavelength: if, starting at a certain point P, we follow along the orbit the phases of the points at a given instant, which are determined by De Broglie’s wave as shown in section 4, then after a complete rotation in either direction we must find for P the same phase again, because the figure represents the state of all the points of the orbit at the same time, and a point cannot have different phases at the same time. Since along a periodic wave the points that have the same phase at the same instant are those separated by a multiple of the wavelength, then the length of a stationary circular electronic orbit must be a multiple of De Broglie’s wavelength.

In principle, we will assume that the electron also contains at least 4 additional parallel plane arrangements of circles of material points essentially similar to that of the middle plane represented in the figure, arranged symmetrically along the dimension perpendicular to the figure, 2 at each side of the middle plane. For obvious reasons of legibility, these 4 additional planes have not been represented. We will also assume that the reason why there exist in each circle just two sets of material points with opposite phases, instead of an infinity of them with any phase, is that, because of the non-linearity postulated in section 2, at each infinitesimal location the potential of the ether is ‘absorbed’ into the nearest pole of non-linearity, resulting in only 2 sets of 137 material points instead of an infinity. This is also essentially what has been explained in section 3, where, in our electron, the points C and D of Fig. 1 would belong to one circular set of 137 material points, the point A to another set of the same type / colour in another circle, and the point B to the other set of material points of the circle of C and D.

In the main picture (a) the real proportions have been respected, with one exception: the small orange arrows that represent the rotation of the electron along its orbit are still far too big, because in one cycle of De Broglie’s wave the electron only advances $1/137^2$ of a complete rotation, or, in other words, it takes 137 cycles of De Broglie’s wave for the electron to achieve $1/137$ of a full rotation, which is the separation between two consecutive ‘dark’ material points in the main figure.

The pictures (b) and (c) represent the progress of De Broglie’s wave along the electron orbit after respectively $1/8$ and $1/4$ cycle. If we take as reference the point of maximum potential, represented in green in the figure, we can see that it has advanced clockwise $1/8$ orbit in (b) and $1/4$ orbit in (c), which is equivalent to 137 times the speed of light. This is possible because De Broglie’s wave is a phase wave, which does not propagate as

the result of a chain of cause-effect events. For example, we can note that the point C does not reach its maximum at time t_2 in picture (c) because this maximum was at B $1/8$ cycle before, but because, $1/8$ cycle before, the point C itself was $1/8$ cycle short of reaching its maximum. Of course, the same considerations apply if we choose as reference the points of minimum potential, represented in orange in the figure, or any other arbitrary reference defined in the phase space of the structure.

So far, what has been discussed in this section is the ground state of the electron of the hydrogen atom, with a circular orbit spanning exactly one De Broglie's wavelength. The more general Bohr-Sommerfeld quantization rule, which applies to trajectories closed but not necessarily circular, with a rotation speed not necessarily uniform, can also be deduced by following and accumulating the phase shifts of the material points along the orbit, but the variations of speed along this trajectory require the use of an integral form for the rule. The calculation is simple, it uses the results of section 3 and it is explained in section 4. An approximate graphical indication of the sequence of phases along an elliptical orbit is represented in Fig. 10, with the same conventions as Fig.9. The figure represents at a given instant the phases of some reference points of the Bohr-Sommerfeld equivalent of the standard quantum state $2s$, with 2 cycles of De Broglie's wave per orbit, the simplest example of elliptical orbit in this model, in which the $1s$ and $2p$ states, outlined in the figure, are circular. In accordance with sections 3 and 4, the distribution of phase references along the orbit is tighter where the speed is higher. We can also note that the material points do not run into each other where the speed decreases, because their speed is too low for that and, also according to sections 3 and 4, in each of its cycles a material point can move only between its nearest neighbours.

Figure 10 – Approximate view of phases along the elliptical electronic orbit $2s$

The fundamental structure of the electron described here cannot be directly extrapolated either to the inner shells of heavy elements, because for them the basic Bohr-Sommerfeld model would result in orbit lengths too short in relation to the Compton wavelength of the electron. A more complete model or calculation involving at least the applicable relativistic effects and the influence of the other electrons of the atom would be required. Even so, it seems likely that all the electrons of whatever shell in any atom keep the shape of cubic / parallelepipedal lattice with Compton-wavelength spacing, because otherwise they would no longer be electrons, and probably not even leptons.

Competing interests

The author has no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

Data Availability Statement

No Data associated in the manuscript.

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(The author has not verified in detail all the experiment reports, let alone the QED calculations, which are really frightening at this degree of precision, even with the help of powerful computers).